

DEVELOPMENT OF ACADEMIC VOCAL PERFORMANCE SKILLS IN MUSIC EDUCATION STUDENTS AS A PEDAGOGICAL ISSUE

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Abstract. *This article examines the pedagogical challenges involved in developing academic vocal performance skills among students majoring in music education. It highlights academic vocal performance as one of the most responsible and complex areas within music education, emphasizing the formation of professional skills and competencies essential for students' musical and pedagogical development.*

Keywords: *academic vocal training, performance, singing, skill, competence, pedagogical problem, music, education, voice, breathing, diction.*

Introduction. Academic vocal performance is an art form that directly influences the human psyche through the power of the voice. It not only provides emotional and volitional enjoyment but also enriches the student's spiritual world. In particular, academic singing performance occupies a special place in the process of musical education. In addition, a vocalist conveys more than just music; they can also express language and meaning, as well as deep feelings through sound and high register intonation. According to this viewpoint, academic vocal performance represents one of the most responsible and complex fields in music education for students. Because it is essential to cultivate stage culture, expressiveness, and artistic thinking in addition to proper vocal production, breathing technique, and diction is what causes this intricacy.

Main Part. In the artistic and musical education system of our republic, the issue of developing students' academic vocal performance skills is currently regarded as a significant scientific and pedagogical problem. This is explained, on the one hand, by the insufficient effectiveness of existing methodological approaches in the educational process. On the other hand, it is associated with new requirements imposed on modern pedagogy, including the use of innovative teaching methods, the implementation of individual and differentiated approaches, and the need to reveal students' creative potential. Consequently, teaching academic singing should incorporate theoretical foundations, scientific analysis, and methodological research. in addition to practical exercises.

Profound transformations in modern society necessitate substantial changes in higher education systems, in state educational standards, qualification requirements for the direction of music education, and, accordingly, in curricula and syllabi. These changes are aimed at more effectively revealing the creative and professional qualities of a graduate of the direction of music education, who are expected to be goal-oriented, proactive, responsible, and competitive. In this context, particular importance is attached to improving students' academic vocal skills, activating their internal potential, and developing self-realization abilities in their future professional activities.

Within the higher education music training process, the development of academic vocal performance skills among prospective music teachers requires specific practical actions

determined by the distinctive characteristics of their professional preparation. The analysis of scientific sources showed that in order to study the development of students' academic singing skills, it is necessary to resort to a set of methodological approaches, namely: systematic, person-oriented, individual, technological.

The systemic approach has two aspects: cognitive (descriptive) and constructive (used in system design). Each of these aspects follows its own implementation algorithm. From the cognitive perspective, the external characteristics of a system—its goal-oriented features and functions as means of achieving objectives—are explained through its internal structure, composition, and organization. From the constructive perspective, as noted by CIS scholar V. N. Protasov, the system design process passes through the following categorical stages: problematic situation, goal, function, composition and structure, and external conditions. At the same time, these categories demonstrate the close interconnection and complementarity of the cognitive and constructive aspects of the systemic approach [3].

The educational process of developing academic vocal performance skills in music education students represents a complex hierarchical structure. It includes goals and objectives at various levels, methodological approaches and principles, the content and functions of structural components, procedures for achieving goals, methods, forms, criteria for determining the level of vocal performance development, as well as assessment and outcomes.

Having been acknowledged that a comprehensive understanding of the system requires not only a general but also a detailed perspective, it should be examined from an overall framework to its individual subsystems, specific elements, and the interactions between them. Practical experience of this system demonstrates that the application of a systemic approach in teaching the subject Vocal Performance is justified and pedagogically appropriate for developing students' academic singing performance skills. This approach makes it possible to study the learner's personality as one mastering academic vocal performance skills, as well as the process of their formation as a component of the higher education pedagogical system. Furthermore, it ensures the integrity of music education and the instructional process, allows for the identification of hierarchical relationships and interactions, and enables the design and clarification of educational models. Thus, the development of students' academic singing performance skills implies the creation of pedagogical conditions for their professional preparation in vocal performance and the stimulation of their self-awareness.

Social pedagogy regards as its primary value a unique personality that is open to mastering new experiences, capable of seeking and consciously selecting appropriate actions in diverse professional and life situations, and striving for the creative realization of internal inclinations. Another scholar from the CIS, V. V. Serikov, defines this concept as “a system of views expressing respect for human dignity and rights, recognition of a person's intrinsic value, and concern for human well-being” [4].

The development of academic singing performance skills among students majoring in music education occupies a special place in professional training. So, this field contributes not only to the development of a student's vocal potential, but also to the formation of artistic thinking and emotional-volitional sensitivity. However, a deeper analysis reveals that this process is not merely a teaching task, but a multifaceted problem containing a range of scientific and pedagogical contradictions.

First and foremost, there is a significant gap between theory and practice. Students acquire theoretical knowledge related to academic singing techniques, breathing, and diction, yet the

practical application of this knowledge often proves challenging. As a result, a certain discrepancy emerges between theoretical foundations and practical performance, which generates pedagogical difficulties in the process of developing academic singing skills. A similar contradiction is observed between traditional teaching methods and modern professional pedagogical technologies. While classical approaches have long dominated academic singing instruction, contemporary educational contexts increasingly require the integration of digital technologies, sound-recording software, and interactive teaching methods.

Another crucial contradiction is observed between the individual approach and standardized curricula. Although each student possesses different vocal range, timbre, and breathing capacity, in the pedagogical field of music education, the teaching process is often carried out on the basis of general requirements, that is, in a collective manner. This does not allow for the full disclosure of individual potential. Additionally, tensions can be observed between national vocal traditions and global academic vocal schools. While academic singing emphasizes voice production, diction, timbre, range, and other performance skills, traditional singing practices prioritize adherence to national stylistic norms and the expressive delivery of poetic text. Students often experience difficulties in reconciling these two directions.

Moreover, an imbalance can be identified between students' internal creative potential and existing methodological approaches. Many methodologies focus primarily on technical skill development, while creativity and musical thinking remain secondary. The most critical contradiction concerns the inconsistency between the competencies formed in higher education institutions and the demands of the contemporary labor market. While there is a growing need for competitive academic vocalists with refined stage culture and multi-genre performance skills, existing educational programs do not yet fully meet these requirements. Therefore, the contradictions arising in the teaching of academic singing performance define it as a scientific and pedagogical problem. Addressing these issues requires the development of modern methodological approaches, the integration of innovative technologies, and the adoption of new pedagogical perspectives aimed at fully realizing students' creative potential.

A learner-centered approach ensures the unconditional priority of musical and educational activities that do not simply shape the vocalist's personality, but rather contribute to and define the professional development of existing individual inclinations, abilities, interests, and psychophysical characteristics. In the context of developing academic singing performance skills among music education students, this approach presupposes systematic work on musical and professional orientation, vocal performance experience, and socio-creative development. Learner-centered education is defined as instruction in which the personality of the music education student, their individuality, progressively acquired academic singing performance skills, and subjective experience are revealed first and subsequently aligned with educational content [5]. In the course of professional and personal development, students are required to engage in continuous work on their academic singing skills and to cultivate self-awareness. This represents a multi-stage process including:

- goal setting: defining long-term personal and socially significant professional objectives;
- short-term goals: acquiring performance experience through daily educational activities with instructors and peers;
- self-design: developing an individual pathway for musical and professional growth;
- independent activity: purpose-oriented self-directed work (musical-creativity, performance, research, etc.);

- identification of dominant musical and creative activities;
- self-awareness: creative expression in musical-pedagogical and vocal performance practices [3].

According to the learner-centered approach, mastering musical and professional activities is ensured through the transformation of educational information into personally meaningful knowledge within the student's professional performance consciousness. Knowledge acquisition occurs within the context of future musical and professional situations that imbue the vocal performance learning process with personal meaning. Local practitioner N. Qahharov notes that an increasing role is played by a "special pedagogical mechanism that places students in new conditions requiring reflection, comprehension, reconsideration of situations, and the formation of new behavioral models" [4]. Thus, the central focus of the educational process is not merely the organization of knowledge acquisition, but the development of students' academic singing performance skills and the formation of their creative individuality.

After being analyzed within this approach, the concept of a learner-centered collective emphasizes the creation of conditions in which the teacher enables each student's self-expression and supports active participation, allowing for the timely adaptation of knowledge to educational and performance practices. Academic singing performance is distinctive in that students may simultaneously belong to several ensembles, such as choirs, vocal ensembles, and solo performance groups. While each student may hold individual interpretative ideas, participation in collective performance requires adherence to shared principles and artistic leadership.

The implementation of learner-centered management within a student collective consists in the fact that, when organizing the educational process, teachers take students' proposals into account. This approach helps learners overcome internal contradictions and gradually contributes not only to improving intragroup dynamics and directing them toward learning, but also to sustaining continuous and purposeful collaborative activity. During the educational process, the teacher should provide assistance to students, seek ways to address emerging problems rather than avoid them, and encourage the search for independent solutions to difficulties encountered in mastering the curriculum. Difficulties may arise during stage performance; therefore, students must develop confidence in their own abilities to overcome problematic situations. In such cases, the teacher's support and guidance in helping students cope with challenges are of particular importance. The teacher's task is to foster independent thinking, performance evaluation skills, and the ability to correct both personal and others' mistakes.

Throughout the learning process, students' capabilities and aspirations should be taken into account. Students should not be allowed to acquire academic singing performance skills superficially, as each learner possesses a certain level of self-awareness and reflective thinking. Active cognitive engagement and a positive attitude toward vocal studies are essential. Thus, the teacher should act as a guiding leader of the educational process while simultaneously considering the specific characteristics of its components and using them to optimize the learning of vocal performance. The methodological approaches discussed above to examining the development of academic singing performance skills among university students have made it possible to understand the multifaceted nature of this phenomenon and to recognize the necessity of conceptualizing such notions as "potential," "vocal," "performance," and "vocal-performance potential."

A student's academic singing performance skills represent a systematically organized individual complex of vocal-performing, musical-creative, intellectual, emotional-volitional, and

artistic resources, shaped by the ethnocultural traditions of Uzbek singing art and ensuring professional activity in the field of vocal performance. In our efforts to develop academic singing performance skills among students majoring in music education, we have adopted the term potential as the semantic content of the concept of personal potential, incorporating within it a system of abilities, knowledge, and skills [5]. The level at which a music education student masters academic singing performance skills reveals the content of personal potential in a deeper and more detailed manner, encompassing such characteristics as inner freedom, independence, meaningfulness of life, readiness for action and internal change, future orientation, and related qualities.

Similarly, local scholars (Sh. Mustafoev et al.) consider personal potential from the standpoint of the resource-based approach, defining it as a system of reserves and capacities that may be manifested in professional activity. It should be emphasized that, in the context of developing academic singing performance skills among music education students, the student's subjective and professional potential may be regarded as an individual source of personal and professional development, representing an inseparable unity of subjective personal qualities and general professional competencies that ensure successful professional activity and the formation of a professional personality. It is particularly important to note that students of music education programs, as future music teachers, are required to master professional skills related to vocal work. In this process, the acquisition of academic singing performance skills emerges as a professionally significant competence that plays a crucial role in their subsequent professional and occupational activities [2].

In the course of conducting this research, we found it necessary to propose the following authorial definition of the concept of personal potential. Personal potential is understood as an individual's integrated capacity, formed as an inseparable professional quality, which unites natural-genetic, socio-personal, and logical components and enables the student to transform surrounding reality through knowledge, abilities, and skills [3]. In examining the processes involved in the development of the creative potential of musically gifted individuals, we rely on the following interpretation of this concept. The creative potential of a student is defined as a complex formation based on an interconnected set of auditory, intellectual, emotional, volitional, and physical abilities, oriented toward the activation of energy resources and realized in musical and creative activity through practical skills [4].

Based on the above analysis of scholarly research, it may be concluded that potential serves as an individual source of personal and professional development for students majoring in music education. It integrates abilities, knowledge, skills, and competencies that ensure success both in the profession and in life, particularly in the development of academic singing performance skills. Turning to the analysis of the content and essence of the concept "vocal," it should be noted that within the field of music education pedagogy, the terms "vocal," "vocal art," "vocal performance," and sometimes "song" are used, often interchangeably. However, it is necessary to clarify their correlation and semantic distinctions. In encyclopedic sources such as the Encyclopedic Dictionary of Music, Music Encyclopedia, and Music Glossary [3], the term vocal does not receive a precise definition in Uzbek; rather, it is explained through notions such as singing, vocalizing, and performing songs.

In our view, vocal emerged as an independent genre in Uzbek musical performance practice during the twentieth century. Vocal art is the art of performing music using the human voice, conveying the ideological and figurative content of a musical work through expressive vocal

means [1]. The prominent Uzbek scholar O. Ibragimov writes in his research that “in its broad sense, vocal should be understood as singing or vocalizing, as well as the performer’s ability to express musical ideas through the singing voice” [5]. As a rule, the concept of vocal functions both as the name of a discipline and as an independent genre of singing, encompassing the mastery of vocal skills and performance techniques. Within its subject matter, it includes vocal technique, voice production, vocal timbre and qualities, breath control, articulation, agogics, and related components. Therefore, vocal art may be rightly understood as a form of performing art aimed at creating artistic images through the rich expressive capabilities of the human voice [3].

Performance activity, in its broad sense, is understood as the achievement of predetermined goals, objectives, and plans in any field of activity, where the goal (a mentally anticipated result and a high level of achievement) serves as the system-forming factor. In a narrower sense, performance activity refers specifically to the art of academic singing performance. The term performance denotes the presentation or reproduction of a work of art before listeners and audiences [4]. In some studies, vocal art is recognized as a form of stage performance art that is not associated with the creation of entirely new works but rather with the creative reinterpretation of works originally created by other composers and performers [3].

Vocal performance is an independent form of artistic creativity in which the performer discovers oneself, reveals creative individuality, and attracts the audience through a properly cultivated voice imbued with personal spirituality. Vocal performance is realized through interpretative and singing actions. Interpretation involves an artistic and creative reading of the composer’s idea through the processes of perceiving, analyzing, and performing a musical work. Creative musical interpretation depends on individual characteristics (musical, intellectual, and others), artistic taste, and the performer’s technical equipment. In students, the development of academic singing performance techniques during specialized instruction contributes to the improvement of vocal qualities such as timbral richness, resonance (metallic brightness), vocal projection, roundness, fullness, “velvety” tone color, dynamic power, evenness, and flexibility of sound production [4].

In academic vocal performance, a singer’s inspired interpretation of a composition implies an understanding of the performance plan, the accumulation of knowledge about the composer’s creative style, the search for expressive vocal means, and the empathetic experience of the artistic image. The complexity of the initial stage of working on a vocal composition in academic singing performance lies in the fact that the process of shaping a musical image is prolonged and, from an external perspective, may appear monotonous and tedious to many. Over an extended period, the student performs the musical material slowly, seemingly detached from personal expressiveness, striving to penetrate the composer’s emotional state, to move beyond the “wall” of musical notation, to anticipate the physical and technical challenges inherent in mastering the work, and to experience internally the emotional tension felt by the composer during its creation.

Future music teachers must clearly understand the rationale behind this process; otherwise, it may seem illogical, awkward, or even impossible at first glance. Therefore, this stage plays a crucial role not only in contemporary globalized systems of music education but also in working on any artistic composition. It requires considerable time and patience, as it cannot be bypassed. One should not prematurely surrender to emotions, nor begin embellishing the interpretation with personal “discoveries” without first forming a clear understanding of the composer’s intent [3].

In the discipline of vocal performance, the mastery of musical works is manifested through the integrated development of interpretative actions (understanding the composer’s intention,

semantic structure, and vocal embodiment), vocal actions (song setting, voice formation, awareness of vocal properties, breath control, articulation, agogics, and related elements), and artistic actions (the expressive spiritual content of performance and the singer's organic stage plasticity).

Conclusion. Each emotion finds its unique physiological expression in the body, such as an increase or decrease in blood pressure, acceleration or slowing of the heartbeat, the level of arousal, specific bodily states, facial expressions, changes in intonation and vocal timbre, and other indicators. As S. L. Rubinstein noted, in everyday life we perceive even the smallest emotional changes in the mood of people around us, especially those close to us, through expressive movements, subtle shifts in facial expression, intonation, and other cues. In the process of vocal performance, a listener may draw similar conclusions about a musical work, based on the full range of expressive moments: intonation, rhythm, pauses, pitch variations, vibrato, and other elements.

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